

Theory of operators and Unitary operators on the power set and the way below relation on transitive binary relational sets

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Received: 15 Jan 2023

Accepted: 13 Mar 2023

Published Online: 01 Jun 2023

Abstract: In this work, S. Abramsky and A. Jung introduced a method to construct a canonical partially ordered set from a pre-order set. The main goal of this monograph is to propose a new representation theory involving below relation (\ll), lower (resp. upper) closure, upper (resp. a lower) cone, convex hull, cofinal set, directed set, domain set and Scott-open (resp Scott-closed) set. We also study the family of all isolated points above (resp. below), isolated point in transitive relational sets. Order preserving monotone and idempotent function between two posets are introduced and discussed, where the latter become representable in all cases, and still rich enough to allow geometric, topological and combinatorial applications. Throughout the text, we shall give evidence of the geometric potential of these new ideas. These concepts extend in many aspects of the known geometric theory of poset, but they also raise new perspectives in the topological world. In particular, we believe that our results and techniques may be of interest in connection with several of the famous conjectures and constructions for algebra and topology. The readers consider them as a source of new concepts, techniques and problems for algebraic theory.

Key words: way below relation, pre-order binary relational sets, poset

1. Introduction

The present paper contains a brief description of partial orders (poset), in particular in posets and lattices, way below relation and more types of functions in transitive relations. A poset consists of a set together with a binary relation that indicates that, for certain pairs of elements in the set, one of the elements precedes the other. Such a relation is called a partial order to reflect the fact that not every pair of elements needs to be related: for some pairs, it may be that neither element precedes the other in the poset. Thus, posets generalize the more familiar total orders. The main aim is to generalize the concepts of poset, by replacing transitive binary relation. In the context of the poset, we propose several new methods of constructing below relation (\ll), lower (resp. upper) closure, upper (resp. a lower) cone, convex hull, cofinal set, directed set, domain set and Scott-open (resp Scott-closed) set. We also study the family of all isolated points above (resp. below), isolated point in transitive relational sets. Order preserving monotone and idempotent function between two posets are introduced and discussed. Several formalisms can be used to express variability in a poset. We take a unified approach to study poset and related concepts. The concept of chain complete poset [15] and the concept of domain [5] are identical although they have different names. In this paper, we stress the importance of the two kinds of operators preserving monotonicity and idempotent property The work of this paper is organized as follows. We shall first briefly introduce poset and related concepts. In Section 2, two kinds of operators are combined, and used to study the relation between Unitary operators on the power set and transitive relations. In Section 3, two kinds of operators above are combined to construct algebraic

lattices, and used to study the relation between The way below relation and some types of functions on transitive relations We first list some necessary notions and relevant properties from the classical order theory in the sequel

Definition 1.1. Let \leq be a binary relation set on $X \neq \phi$. Then;

- (1) \leq is called reflexive (RR for short) iff $\forall x \in X, x \leq x$ [9];
- (2) \leq is called antisymmetric (AR for short) iff $\forall x, y \in X, x \leq y$ and $y \leq x \Rightarrow x = y$ [9];
- (3) \leq is called transitive (TR for short)) iff $\forall x, y, z \in X, x \leq y$ and $y \leq z \Rightarrow x \leq z$ [9];
- (4) \leq is called symetric (SR for short) iff $\forall x, y \in X, x \leq y \Rightarrow y \leq x$ [9];
- (5) \leq is called interpolative (denoted by, IR) iff $\forall x, z \in X,$ with $x \leq z, \exists y \in X$ s.t. $x \leq y \leq z$ [3].
- (6) If \leq satisfies the conditions (1), (2) and (3), then (X, \leq) is called partialy order set (Poset) [13];
- (7) If \leq satisfies the conditions (1), and (3), then (X, \leq) is called pre-orderd set (Quasi set) (PRS for short) [9];
- (8) If \leq satisfies the conditions (1), (2), (3) and (4), then (X, \leq) is called an equivalence set,
- (9) If \leq satisfies the conditions (3) and (5), then (X, \leq) is a Continuous information system [7].
- (10) If \leq satisfies the conditions (3), and $\forall x \in X,$ and for every finite subset A of X the following axiom holds: if $\forall y \in A, y \leq x$ then $\exists z \in X$ s.t. $\forall y \in A, y \leq z$ and $z \leq x,$ then (X, \leq) is abstract basis [12].

Definition 1.2. For any poset $X,$ let $A, B, \lambda \subseteq X.$ Then:

- (1) The lower (resp. upper) bounded subset in X of λ is denoted by $lb(\lambda)$ (resp. $ub(\lambda)$) and defined as follows:
 $lb(\lambda) = \{x \in X : \forall y \in \lambda, x \leq y\}$ (resp. $ub(\lambda) = \{x \in X : \forall y \in \lambda, y \leq x\}$).
- (2) The subset of least (resp. largest) elements of a subset λ is denoted by $le(\lambda)$ (resp. $la(\lambda)$) and defined as follows:
 $le(\lambda) = \{x \in \lambda : \forall y \in \lambda, x \leq y\}$ (resp. $la(\lambda) = \{x \in \lambda : \forall y \in \lambda, y \leq x\}$). Each element in $le(\lambda)$ (resp. $la(\lambda)$) is acled a least (resp. largest) element of λ [9].
- (3) The infimum (resp. supremum) subset in X is denoted by $\bigwedge(\lambda)$ (resp. $\bigvee(\lambda)$) and defined as follows:
 $\bigwedge(\lambda) = la(lb(\lambda))$ (resp. $\bigvee(\lambda) = le(ub(\lambda))$). Each element in $\bigwedge(\lambda)$ (resp. $\bigvee(\lambda)$) is acled a infimum (resp. supremum) element of λ [9].
- (4) The lower (resp. upper) closure in X of λ is denoted by $\downarrow \lambda$ (resp. $\uparrow \lambda$) and defined as follows:
 $\downarrow \lambda = \{x \in X : \exists y \in \lambda$ s.t. $x \leq y\}$ (resp. $\uparrow \lambda = \{x \in X : \exists y \in \lambda$ s.t. $y \leq x\}$)[3];
- (5) An upper (resp. a lower) cone of X iff $\exists x \in \lambda$ s.t. $\lambda = \uparrow x$ (resp. $\lambda = \downarrow x$)[3].
- (6) The convex hull A is denoted by $\uparrow \downarrow A$ and defined as follows: $\uparrow \downarrow A = \downarrow A \cap \uparrow A$ [3];
- (7) Let $A, B \subseteq X.$ B is called cofinal in A iff $B \subseteq A \subseteq \downarrow(B)$ [3].
- (8) λ is called directed subset of X iff $\lambda \neq \phi$ and $\forall x, y \in \lambda, \exists z \in \lambda$ s.t. $x \leq z$ and $y \leq z$ [3];
- (9) \leq is called a domain iff for every directed subset λ of $X, \bigvee(\lambda)$ exists.
- (10) A subset λ of the domain (resp. Poset) X is called directed closed (d -closed for short) iff \forall directed subset D of $\lambda, \bigvee(D) \in \lambda;$ [3]
- (11) A subset λ of the Poset X is called Scott-closed iff λ is d -closed lower subset of X [11] ;
- (12) λ is called d -(resp. Scott-) open iff λ^c d -(resp. Scott-) closed [3, 11];

Proposition 1.1.[5] Let (X, \leq) be a poset, let $\lambda \subseteq X$ such that $\bigvee(\lambda)$ exists. Then $\bigcap_{x \in \lambda} \uparrow x = \uparrow \bigvee(\lambda).$

Proposition 1.2.[5] Let (X, \leq) be a poset, let $\lambda, \mu \subseteq X$ and let $\lambda \subseteq \mu.$ If $\bigvee(\lambda) \neq \phi$ and $\bigvee(\mu) \neq \phi.$ Then $\bigvee(\lambda) \leq \bigvee(\mu).$

Proposition 1.3.[5] Let (X, \leq) be a poset. Let $A, B \subseteq X$, Then:

- (1) $\uparrow A$ is convex;
- (2) A is convex iff $\uparrow A = A$;
- (3) If $A \subseteq B$. and B is convex then, $\uparrow A \subseteq B$.

Proposition 1.4.[5] Let (X, \leq) be a poset. If λ be an upper subset of X , then it is d -open.

Proposition 1.5.[5] Let (X, \leq) be a poset, and let λ be a convex subset of X . and $(\downarrow \lambda)$ is d -closed, then λ so is.

Proposition 1.6.[5] Let (X, \leq) be a poset, and $\forall j \in J$, λ_j be a family of lower (resp. upper) subset of X , then $(\bigcap_{j \in J} \lambda_j)$ and $(\bigcup_{j \in J} \lambda_j)$ are lower (resp. upper) subsets of X

Proposition 1.7.(Corollary page 45.[5]).Let (X, \leq) be a poset. If λ is directed subset iff $(\downarrow \lambda)$ so is.

Proposition 1.8.[5] Let (X, \leq) be a poset, and let $\lambda, \mu \subseteq X$ such that $(\downarrow \lambda) = (\downarrow \mu)$. If λ is directed subset iff μ so is.

Proposition 1.9.[5] Let (X, \leq) be a poset, and let $x, y \in X$. Then:

- (1) $x \leq y \Leftrightarrow x \in \downarrow y \Leftrightarrow \downarrow x \subseteq \downarrow y \Leftrightarrow y \in \uparrow x \Leftrightarrow \uparrow x \subseteq \uparrow y$;
- (2) $x \in \downarrow x \Leftrightarrow x \in \uparrow x$;
- (3) $\downarrow x \cap \uparrow x = \{x\}$.

Proposition 1.10.[5]. Let (X, \leq) be a poset, and let λ_j is a an upper (resp.lower) subsets of $(X_j) \forall j \in J$, then $\prod_{j \in J} (\lambda_j)$ is a an upper (resp. lower) subsets of $\prod_{j \in J} X_j$.

Proposition 1.11.[5] Let (X, \leq) be a poset $\{(X_j, \leq_j) : j \in J\}$ be a family of a poset, and let $\lambda_j \subseteq X_j \forall j \in J$. Then

- (1) $\uparrow (\prod_{j \in J} \lambda_j) = (\prod_{j \in J} \uparrow (\lambda_j))$
- (2) $\downarrow (\prod_{j \in J} \lambda_j) = (\prod_{j \in J} \downarrow (\lambda_j))$

Remark 1.1. Each point of X is an upper bound of the empty set. Then $\bigvee(\phi)$ exists iff X has a least element \perp . In this case $\bigvee(\phi) = \perp$.

Proposition 1.12.[5] Let (X, \leq) be a poset, and let $\lambda, \mu \subseteq X$. If μ is directed subset and cofinal in λ , then λ is directed subset and $\bigvee(\lambda) = \bigvee(\mu)$.

Definition 1.3. (1) For any poset X , :Let $x, y \in X$. We say x below (resp. y is way above) y (resp. x), denoted by $x \ll y$ iff $\forall D \subseteq X$, s.t. D is directed subset of X with $\bigvee D$ exists and $y \leq \bigvee D$, $\exists d \in D$ s.t. $x \leq d$. The family of all elements in X each of which way above (resp. way below) x is denoted and defined as follows: $\uparrow x = \{y \in X : x \ll y\}$ (resp. $\downarrow x = \{y \in X : y \ll x\}$ [11];

(2) Let $x \in X$. If $x \ll x$, then x is said to be isolated. The family of all isolated points above (resp. below) $x \in X$ is denoted and defined by: $\uparrow^\circ x = \{y \in X : y \ll y \text{ and } x \leq y\}$ (resp. $\downarrow^\circ x = \{y \in X : y \ll y \text{ and } y \leq x\}$ [11].

Proposition 1.13.[5] Let (X, \leq) be a domain,.If X has a least element \perp , then $\perp \ll x$ holds for all $x \in X$.

Proposition 1.14.[5]. Let (X, \leq) be a domain, and let D is directed subset of X . such that $x = \bigvee(D)$ and x is isolated. Then $x \in D$.

Definition 1.7. [9] Let (X, \leq_1) and (X, \leq_2) be a poset, and let $f : (X, \leq_1) \rightarrow (Y, \leq_2)$ be a function. Then

- (1) f is monotone iff $f(\lambda) \leq_2 f(\mu)$, whenever $\lambda \leq_1 \mu$,
- (2) f is called order preserving (monotone) iff $f(x_1) \leq_2 f(x_2)$, whenever $x_1 \leq_1 x_2$.

Lemma 1.1. [9] Let X be a set and let $f : X \rightarrow X$ be a function. Then f is idempotent iff $f(X) = fix(f)$, where $fix(f) = \{x \in X : f(x) = x\}$.

2- Operators and Unitary operators on the power set of TR

Definition 2.1. A TR is a pair (X, \leq) where $X \neq \phi$ and \leq is a transitive binary relations set.

Example 2.1. Poset, equivalence set, PRS , Continuous information system and abstract basis are TR .

The following diagram illustrates some relations between some types of TR

Remark 2.1. Abstract basis \Rightarrow Continuous information system, the converse is not true, so give the following example

Example 2.2. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and let $\leq = \{(a, a), (b, b), (a, c), (b, c)\}$, because

$$\begin{aligned}
 a \leq a &\Rightarrow \exists a \in X \text{ s.t., } a \leq a \leq a; \\
 b \leq b &\Rightarrow \exists b \in X \text{ s.t., } b \leq b \leq b; \\
 a \leq c &\Rightarrow \exists a \in X \text{ s.t., } a \leq a \leq c, \text{ and} \\
 b \leq c &\Rightarrow \exists b \in X \text{ s.t., } b \leq b \leq c.
 \end{aligned}$$

Then \leq transitive and interpolative. Now, Let $\lambda = \{a, b\}$. Then $a \leq c$ and $b \leq c$, but $\forall x \in X, x \not\leq c$. Hence (X, \leq) is not abstract basis.

Definition 2.2. Let $\{(X_j, \leq_j) : j \in J\}$ be a family of TR . The product relation \leq on $\prod_{j \in J} X_j$ of $\{\leq_j : j \in J\}$ is defined as follows: $(x_j)_{j \in J} \leq (y_j)_{j \in J}$ iff $x_j \leq_j y_j \quad \forall j \in J$.

Definition 2.3. Let (X, \leq) be a TR . the dual of \leq is denoted and defined as follows: $\leq^d = \{(x, y) : (y, x) \in \leq\}$.

Theorem 2.1. $\{(X_j, \leq_j) : j \in J\}$ be a family of TR , $(\prod_{j \in J} X_j, \leq)$ is TR , where \leq is the product of $\{\leq_j : j \in J\}$.

Proof Let $(x_j)_{j \in J} \leq (y_j)_{j \in J}$, $(y_j)_{j \in J} \leq (z_j)_{j \in J}$. Then $\forall j \in J, x_j \leq_j y_j$ and $y_j \leq_j z_j$ so that $\forall j \in J, x_j \leq_j z_j$. Thus $(x_j)_{j \in J} \leq (z_j)_{j \in J}$. Then \leq is TR . Hence $(\prod_{j \in J} X_j, \leq)$ is TR .

Definition 2.4. Let (X, \leq) be a *TR*. Then:

- (1) The lower (resp. upper) bounded subset in X of λ is denoted by $lb(\lambda)$ (resp. $ub(\lambda)$) and defined as follows:
 $lb(\lambda) = \{x \in X : \forall y \in \lambda, x \leq y\}$ (resp. $ub(\lambda) = \{x \in X : \forall y \in \lambda, y \leq x\}$).
- (2) The minimal (resp. maximal) subset in X of λ is denoted by $\min(\lambda)$ (resp. $\max(\lambda)$) and defined as follows:
 $\min(\lambda) = \{x \in \lambda : \text{if } y \in \lambda, \text{ and } y \leq x, \text{ then } x = y\}$ (resp. $\max(\lambda) = \{x \in \lambda : \text{if } y \in \lambda, \text{ and } x \leq y, \text{ then } x = y\}$).
- (3) The subset of least (resp. largest) elements of a subset λ is denoted by $le(\lambda)$ (resp. $la(\lambda)$) and defined as follows:
 $le(\lambda) = \{x \in \lambda : \forall y \in \lambda, x \leq y\}$ (resp. $la(\lambda) = \{x \in \lambda : \forall y \in \lambda, y \leq x\}$). Each element in $le(\lambda)$ (resp. $la(\lambda)$) is called a least (resp. largest) element of λ .
- (4) The infimum (resp. supremum) subset in X of λ is denoted by $\bigwedge(\lambda)$ (resp. $\bigvee(\lambda)$) and defined as follows:
 $\bigwedge(\lambda) = le(lb(\lambda))$ (resp. $\bigvee(\lambda) = la(ub(\lambda))$). Each element in $\bigwedge(\lambda)$ (resp. $\bigvee(\lambda)$) is called an infimum (resp. supremum) element of λ .
- (5) The lower (resp. upper) closure in X of λ is denoted by $\downarrow \lambda$ (resp. $\uparrow \lambda$) and defined as follows:
 $\downarrow \lambda = \{x \in X : \exists y \in \lambda \text{ s.t. } x \leq y\}$ (resp. $\uparrow \lambda = \{x \in X : \exists y \in \lambda \text{ s.t. } y \leq x\}$).
- (6) An upper (resp. a lower) cone of X iff $\exists x \in \lambda \text{ s.t. } \lambda = \uparrow x$ (resp. $\lambda = \downarrow x$).
- (7) The convex hull A is denoted by $\updownarrow A$ and defined as follows: $\updownarrow A = \downarrow A \cap \uparrow A$.
- (8) Let $A, B \subseteq X$. B is called cofinal in A iff $B \subseteq A \subseteq \downarrow(B)$.
- (9) Let (X, \leq) be a *TR*, then \leq is called a domain iff for every directed subset λ of X , $\bigvee(\lambda)$ exists.

Remark 2.2 In [13], If (X, \leq) is a posets, then concepts $le(\lambda)$, $la(\lambda)$, $\bigwedge(\lambda)$, $\bigvee(\lambda)$ is singleton. if it exists. but in *TR* need not be singleton. so give the following example,

Example 2.3. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d, e\}$ and let $\leq = \{(a, a), (b, b), (a, b), (b, a)\}$. Then (X, \leq) be a *TR*, and $\bigvee(\{a, b\}) = \bigwedge(\{a, b\}) = le(\{a, b\}) = la(\{a, b\}) = \{a, b\}$.

Theorem 2.2 Let (X, \leq) be a *TR*. Then the following statements are satisfied;

- (1) x is an upper (resp. lower) bounded of a subset λ of a *TR* (X, \leq) iff x is an lower (resp. upper) bounded of (X, \leq^d) .
- (2) x is least (resp. largest) elements of a subset λ of a *TR* (X, \leq) iff x is largest (resp. least) elements of a subset λ of a *TR* (X, \leq^d) .
- (3) $x \in \bigvee(\lambda)$ (resp., $\bigwedge(\lambda)$) of a *TR* (X, \leq) iff $x \in \bigwedge(\lambda)$ (resp., $\bigvee(\lambda)$) of a *TR* (X, \leq^d) .
- (4) $\downarrow \lambda$ (resp. $\uparrow \lambda$) of a *TR* (X, \leq) equals $\uparrow \lambda$ (resp. $\downarrow \lambda$) of a *TR* (X, \leq^d) .
- (5) minimal (λ) (resp. maximal (λ)) of a *TR* (X, \leq) equals maximal (λ) (resp. minimal (λ)) of a *TR* (X, \leq^d) .

Remark 2.3 Let (X, \leq) be a *PRS*, then $\forall \lambda \subseteq X, \lambda \subseteq \downarrow \lambda$ (resp., $\lambda \subseteq \uparrow \lambda$), but if (X, \leq) be a *TR*, then λ need not be a subset of $\downarrow \lambda$ (resp., $\uparrow \lambda$), so give the following example.

Example 2.4. Let $X = \{x, y, z\}$ and let $\leq = \{(x, x), (x, y)\}$. Take $\lambda = X$. Then $X \not\subseteq \{x\} = \downarrow X$ (resp., $X \not\subseteq \{x, y\} = \uparrow X$).

Remark 2.4 Let (X, \leq) be a *PRS*, then $\forall \lambda \subseteq X, \lambda \subseteq \downarrow \lambda \subseteq \downarrow(\downarrow \lambda)$ (resp., $\uparrow \lambda \subseteq \uparrow(\uparrow \lambda)$), but if (X, \leq) be a *TR*, then λ need not be a subset of $\downarrow(\downarrow \lambda)$ (resp., $\uparrow(\uparrow \lambda)$), so give the following example.

Example 2.5. Let $X = \{x, y, z\}$ and let $\leq = \{(x, x), (x, y)\}$. Take $\lambda = X$. Then $\uparrow(\uparrow\lambda) = \{x\} \not\supseteq \uparrow\lambda$. (resp., $\downarrow(\downarrow\lambda) = \{x\} \not\supseteq \downarrow\lambda = \{x, y\}$).

Remark 2.5 Let (X, \leq) be a *PRS*, then $\forall \lambda \subseteq X$, $\lambda \subseteq \uparrow\lambda$, but if (X, \leq) be a *TR*, then λ need not be a subset of $\uparrow\lambda$, so give the following example.

Example 2.6. Let $X = \{x, y, z\}$ and let $\leq = \{(x, x), (x, y)\}$. Take $\lambda = X$. Then $\uparrow\lambda = (\uparrow\lambda) \cap (\downarrow\lambda) = \{x\} \cap \{x, y\} = \{x\} \not\supseteq \lambda$.

Remark 2.6 Let (X, \leq) be a *PRS*, then $\forall \lambda \subseteq X$, $\uparrow\lambda \subseteq \uparrow(\uparrow\lambda)$, but if (X, \leq) be a *TR*, then $\uparrow\lambda$ need not be a subset of $\uparrow(\uparrow\lambda)$, so give the following example.

Example 2.7. Let $X = \{x, y, z, l\}$ and let $\leq = \{(x, y), (y, z), (x, z)\}$. Take $\lambda = \{x, y, z\}$ of X . Then $\downarrow\lambda = \{x, y\}$ and $\uparrow\lambda = \{y, z\}$, then $\uparrow\lambda = (\uparrow\lambda) \cap (\downarrow\lambda) = \{y\}$. Thus $\uparrow(\uparrow\lambda) = \uparrow(\{y\}) = (\uparrow\{y\}) \cap (\downarrow\{y\}) = \{x\} \cap \{z\} = \phi$. Hence $\uparrow\lambda \not\subseteq \uparrow(\uparrow\lambda)$.

Theorem 2.3 Let (X, \leq) be a *TR*, and let $\{\lambda_j : j \in J\}$ be a family of subset of X . Then:

- (1) $\downarrow(\bigcup_{j \in J} \lambda_j) = \bigcup_{j \in J} \downarrow(\lambda_j)$
- (2) $\uparrow(\bigcup_{j \in J} \lambda_j) = \bigcup_{j \in J} \uparrow(\lambda_j)$
- (3) $\downarrow(\bigcap_{j \in J} \lambda_j) \subseteq \bigcap_{j \in J} \downarrow(\lambda_j)$
- (4) $\uparrow(\bigcap_{j \in J} \lambda_j) \subseteq \bigcap_{j \in J} \uparrow(\lambda_j)$

Proof (1) Let $x \in \downarrow(\bigcup_{j \in J} \lambda_j) \Leftrightarrow \exists y \in (\bigcup_{j \in J} \lambda_j)$ such that $x \leq y \Leftrightarrow \exists \lambda_j$ such that $j \in J$, $y \in \lambda_j$, $x \leq y \Leftrightarrow x \in \downarrow(\lambda_j)$ for some $j \in J \Leftrightarrow x \in \bigcup_{b \in F_2} \downarrow(\lambda_j)$.

(2) $x \in \uparrow(\bigcup_{j \in J} \lambda_j) \Leftrightarrow \exists y \in (\bigcup_{j \in J} \lambda_j)$ such that $y \leq x \Leftrightarrow \exists \lambda_j$ such that $j \in J$, $y \in \lambda_j$, $y \leq x \Leftrightarrow x \in \uparrow(\lambda_j)$ for some $j \in J \Leftrightarrow x \in \bigcup_{j \in J} \uparrow(\lambda_j)$.

(3) $x \in \downarrow(\bigcap_{j \in J} \lambda_j) \Rightarrow \exists y \in (\bigcap_{j \in J} \lambda_j)$ such that $x \leq y \Rightarrow \forall j \in J$, $\exists y \in \lambda_j$, such that $x \leq y \Rightarrow x \in \downarrow(\lambda_j) \forall j \in J \Rightarrow x \in \bigcap_{j \in J} \downarrow(\lambda_j)$; and

(4) $x \in \uparrow(\bigcap_{j \in J} \lambda_j) \Rightarrow \exists y \in (\bigcap_{j \in J} \lambda_j)$ such that $y \leq x \Rightarrow \forall j \in J$, $\exists y \in \lambda_j$, such that $y \leq x \Rightarrow x \in \uparrow(\lambda_j) \forall j \in J \Rightarrow x \in \bigcap_{j \in J} \uparrow(\lambda_j)$.

The following theorem is a generalization of the corresponding result in Proposition 1.1.

Theorem 2.4 Let (X, \leq) be a *TR*, and let $\lambda \subseteq X$ such that $\bigvee(\lambda)$ exists. Then $\bigcap_{x \in \lambda} \uparrow x = \uparrow \bigvee(\lambda)$.

Proof Let $y \in \bigcap_{x \in \lambda} \uparrow x \Leftrightarrow \forall x \in \lambda$, $y \in \uparrow x \Leftrightarrow y \geq x \forall x \in \lambda \Leftrightarrow y \in \uparrow \bigvee(\lambda)$.

The following theorem is a generalization of the corresponding result in Proposition 1.2.

Theorem 2.5 Let (X, \leq) be a TR , and let $\lambda, \mu \subseteq X$ and let $\lambda \subseteq \mu$. If $\bigvee(\lambda) \neq \phi$ and $\bigvee(\mu) \neq \phi$. Then $\forall \alpha \in \bigvee(\lambda), \forall \beta \in \bigvee(\mu), \alpha \leq \beta$.

Proof If $\forall x \in ub(\lambda), \forall y \in ub(\mu), y \geq x$. If $\alpha \in \bigvee(\lambda) = le(ub(\lambda))$ and $\beta \in \bigvee(\mu) = le(ub(\mu))$, $\alpha \leq x \forall x \in ub(\lambda)$, so that $\alpha \leq y \forall y \in ub(\mu)$. so that $\alpha \leq \beta$.

Definition 2.4. Let (X, \leq) be a TR , and let $\lambda, \mu \subseteq X$. λ is called:

- (1) An lower (resp. upper) subset of X iff $\downarrow \lambda \subseteq \lambda$ (resp. $\uparrow \lambda \subseteq \lambda$). The family of all lower (resp. upper) subset in λ will denoted by $LS(\lambda)$ (resp., $US(\lambda)$),
- (2) A directed (resp. filtered) subset of X iff $\lambda \neq \phi$ and every $x \neq y$ in λ , $\exists z \in \lambda \cap lb(\{x, y\})$;
- (3) The ideal (resp. filter) subset of X iff λ is directed lower subset (resp. filtered upper subset) in X ;
- (4) A principal ideal (resp. principal filter) of X iff $\max(\lambda) \neq \phi$ (resp. $\min(\lambda) \neq \phi$);
- (5) A bounded subset from above (resp. below) of X iff $ub(\lambda) \neq \phi$ (resp. $lb(\lambda) \neq \phi$);
- (6) A cofinal in μ iff $\lambda \subseteq \mu \subseteq \downarrow(\lambda)$;
- (7) A convex subset of X iff $\forall x, y \in \lambda$ such that $x \leq z$ and $z \leq y, z \in \lambda$;
- (8) An upper (resp. lower) cone of X iff $\exists x \in \lambda$ such that $\lambda = \uparrow x$ (resp. $\lambda = \downarrow x$);
- (9) A d -closed subset iff \forall directed subset D of X such that $D \subseteq \lambda$, we have $\bigvee(D) \subseteq \lambda$;
- (10) A d -open subset of X iff λ^c is a d -closed subset;
- (11) A Scott-closed subset of X iff λ is d -closed lower subset ;
- (12) A Scott-open subset of X iff λ is d -closed upper subset of ;

The following theorem is a generalization of the corresponding result in Proposition 1.3.

Theorem 2.6 Let (X, \leq) be a TR , and let λ be a convex subset of X , $\uparrow \downarrow \lambda \subseteq \lambda$.

Proof $y \in \uparrow \downarrow \lambda = (\uparrow \lambda) \cap (\downarrow \lambda)$ so that $y \in \uparrow \lambda$ and $y \in \downarrow \lambda$ so that $\exists x, z \in \lambda$ with $x \leq y$ and $y \leq z$. Since λ convex $y \in \lambda$

Remark 2.7 Let (X, \leq) be a PRS , then $\forall \lambda \subseteq X, \lambda \subseteq \uparrow \lambda$ and $\lambda \subseteq \downarrow \lambda$ so that $\lambda \subseteq (\uparrow \downarrow \lambda)$, but if (X, \leq) be a TR , $\lambda \subseteq \uparrow \lambda$ and $\lambda \subseteq \downarrow \lambda$ so that $\lambda \subseteq (\uparrow \downarrow \lambda)$ need not be true, so give the following example.

Example 2.8. Let $X = \{x, y, z, l, m\}$ Now $\leq = \{(x, y), (y, l), (x, l), (l, l)\}$. is TR . Take $\lambda = \{x, y, z\}$ of X . Then $\downarrow \lambda = \{x\}$ so that $\lambda \not\subseteq \downarrow \lambda$ and $\uparrow \lambda = \{y, l\}$, so that $\lambda \not\subseteq \uparrow \lambda$ and $\uparrow \downarrow \lambda = (\uparrow \lambda) \cap (\downarrow \lambda) = \phi$ so that $\lambda \not\subseteq \uparrow \downarrow \lambda$.

The following theorem is a generalization of the corresponding result in Proposition 1.3(1)

Theorem 2.7 Let (X, \leq) be a TR , Then $\uparrow \downarrow \lambda$ is convex.

Proof Let $x, y \in \uparrow \downarrow \lambda = (\uparrow \lambda) \cap (\downarrow \lambda)$ and let $x \leq z \leq y$. Then $\exists x_1 \in \lambda$ such that $y \leq y_1$ and $\exists x_1 \in \lambda$ such that $x_1 \leq x$ so $x_1 \leq x \leq z \leq y \leq y_1$. Because (X, \leq) is a TR , Then $z \in \uparrow \downarrow \lambda$ so that $\uparrow \downarrow \lambda$ is convex.

Theorem 2.8 Let (X, \leq) be a TR , and let $\lambda \subseteq X$, Then:

λ is a d -open subset of X iff \forall directed subset D of X such that $\bigvee(D) \cap \lambda \neq \phi$, we have $D \cap \lambda \neq \phi$

Proof Logically: for $\lambda \subseteq X$, Let E is a family of all directed subset of of X , and $P \equiv D \in E$, $Q \equiv D \subseteq \lambda'$, and

$R \equiv' \bigvee(D) \subseteq \lambda'$. Now λ is a d -closed $\equiv P \wedge (Q \Rightarrow R) \equiv P \wedge (\neg R \Rightarrow \neg Q)$. So λ^c is a d -open iff $\forall D \in E$ such that $\bigvee(D) \cap \lambda^c \neq \phi$, we have $D \cap \lambda^c \neq \phi$, where $\neg R$ and $\neg Q$ are the negations of R and Q respectively. We can simply say that, μ is a d -open iff $\forall D \in E$ such that $\bigvee(D) \cap \mu \neq \phi$, and $D \cap \mu \neq \phi$.

The following theorem is a generalization of the corresponding result in Proposition 1.4.

Theorem 2.9 Let (X, \leq) be a TR , and let λ be an upper subset of X , then it is d -open.

Proof Let λ be an upper subset of X and let D be a directed subset of λ . Now, $m \in \bigvee(D)$ implies that $\exists k \in D \subseteq \lambda$ such that $k \leq m$. Then $m \in (\uparrow \lambda) \subseteq \lambda$, so that $m \in \lambda$. Thus $\bigvee(D) \subseteq \lambda$.

The following theorem is a generalization of the corresponding result in Proposition 1.5.

Theorem 2.10 Let (X, \leq) be a PRS , and let λ be a convex subset of X . If $(\downarrow \lambda)$ is d -closed, then λ so is.

Proof Let D be a directed subset of λ . Now. Because \leq is reflexive, then $D \in \lambda \subseteq (\downarrow \lambda)$. Since $(\downarrow \lambda)$ is d -closed, then $\bigvee(D) \subseteq (\downarrow \lambda)$. So $\forall m \in \bigvee(D) \exists x \in \lambda$ such that $m \leq x$. Since $D \neq \phi$, then $\exists d \in D$ such that $d \leq m$. Now, $d \leq m \leq x$. Since λ is convex, then $m \in \lambda$ so that $\bigvee(D) \subseteq \lambda$. Hence λ is d -closed.

Theorem 2.11 Let (X, \leq) be a TR , and let λ be a subset of X , then

- (1) $(\downarrow \lambda) \subseteq \lambda$ iff $(\uparrow \lambda^c) \subseteq \lambda^c$;
- (2) $(\uparrow \lambda) \subseteq \lambda$ iff $(\downarrow \lambda^c) \subseteq \lambda^c$.

Proof (1) \Rightarrow : Let $x \in (\uparrow \lambda^c)$ implies that $\exists y \in \lambda^c$ such that $y \leq x$ implies that $\exists y \notin \lambda$ such that $y \leq x$ implies that $\exists y \notin (\downarrow \lambda)$ such that $y \leq x$ implies that $\forall z \in \lambda, y \not\leq z$ and $y \leq x$ implies that $x \notin \lambda$ implies that $x \in \lambda^c$;

\Leftarrow : Let $x \in (\downarrow \lambda)$ implies that $\exists y \in \lambda$ such that $x \leq y$ implies that $\exists y \notin \lambda^c$ such that $x \leq y$ implies that $\exists y \notin (\uparrow \lambda^c)$ such that $x \leq y$ implies that $\forall z \in \lambda^c, z \not\leq y$ and $x \leq y$ implies that $x \notin \lambda^c$ implies that $x \in \lambda$.

- (2) Not need to prove this case, because this statement is equivalent to (1).

Corollary 2.1. Let (X, \leq) be a TR , and let λ be a subset of X , then λ is lower (resp. an upper) subset of X iff λ^c is upper (resp. an lower).

The following theorem is a generalization of the corresponding result in Proposition 1.6.

Theorem 2.12 Let (X, \leq) be a TR , and let λ_j be a family of lower (resp. upper) subset of X , then

$(\bigcap_{j \in J} \lambda_j)$ and $(\bigcup_{j \in J} \lambda_j)$ are lower (resp. upper) subsets of X

Proof. (1) From Theorem 2.3 (3) we have $\downarrow (\bigcap_{j \in J} \lambda_j) \subseteq \bigcap_{j \in J} \downarrow (\lambda_j)$ so that $\downarrow (\bigcap_{j \in J} \lambda_j) \subseteq \bigcap_{j \in J} (\lambda_j)$. Hence

$\bigcap_{j \in J} (\lambda_j)$ is lower subset of X ; And

From Theorem 2.3 (4) we have $\uparrow (\bigcap_{j \in J} \lambda_j) \subseteq \bigcap_{j \in J} \uparrow (\lambda_j)$ so that $\uparrow (\bigcap_{j \in J} \lambda_j) \subseteq \bigcap_{j \in J} (\lambda_j)$. Hence $\bigcap_{j \in J} (\lambda_j)$ is upper subset of X .

(2) Let $x \in \downarrow (\bigcup_{j \in J} \lambda_j)$ implies that $\exists j \in J$ such that $y \leq \lambda_j$ and $x \leq y$ implies that $x \in \downarrow (\lambda_j)$ implies that $x \in (\lambda_j)$ implies that $x \in (\bigcup_{j \in J} \lambda_j)$. Hence $(\bigcup_{j \in J} \lambda_j)$ is lower subset of X ; And

Let $x \in \uparrow (\bigcup_{j \in J} \lambda_j)$ implies that $\exists j \in J$ such that $y \leq \lambda_j$ and $y \leq x$ implies that $x \in \uparrow (\lambda_j)$ implies that $x \in (\lambda_j)$ implies that $x \in (\bigcup_{j \in J} \lambda_j)$. Hence $(\bigcup_{j \in J} \lambda_j)$ is upper subset of X .

Lemma 2.1 Let (X, \leq) be a *PRS*. If λ is directed subset, then $(\downarrow \lambda)$ so is.

Proof. Let $x_1, x_2 \in (\downarrow \lambda)$ such that $x_1 \neq x_2$. Then $\exists y_1, y_2 \in \lambda$ such that $x_1 \leq y_1, x_2 \leq y_2$. So $\exists x \in ub(\{x_1, x_2\})$. Since $\lambda \subseteq (\downarrow \lambda)$, then $x \in (\downarrow \lambda)$. Thus $x \in (\downarrow \lambda) \cap ub(\{x_1, x_2\})$. Hence $(\downarrow \lambda)$ is directed subset.

The following Corollary is a generalization of the corresponding result in Proposition 1.7.

Corollary 2.2. Let (X, \leq) be a *PRS*. If λ is directed subset iff $(\downarrow \lambda)$ so is.

The following theorem is a generalization of the corresponding result in Proposition 1.8.

Theorem 2.13 Let (X, \leq) be a *PRS*, and let $\lambda, \mu \subseteq X$ such that $(\downarrow \lambda) = (\downarrow \mu)$. If λ is directed subset, then μ so is

Proof. From Lemma 2.1, since λ is directed subset, then $(\downarrow \lambda)$ is directed subset, implies that $(\downarrow \mu)$ is directed subset. Now prove that μ is directed subset, let $x_1, x_2 \in \mu$ such that $x_1 \neq x_2$, then $x_1, x_2 \in (\downarrow \mu)$. So $\exists x \in (\downarrow \mu)$ such that $x \in (\downarrow \mu) \cap ub(\{x_1, x_2\})$. Then $\exists y \in \mu$ such that $x \leq y$. Now $x_1 \leq x \leq y$ and $x_2 \leq x \leq y$ so that $y \in \mu \cap ub(\{x_1, x_2\})$. Hence μ is directed subset.

Corollary 2.3. Let (X, \leq) be a *PRS*, and let $\lambda, \mu \subseteq X$ such that $(\downarrow \lambda) = (\downarrow \mu)$. If λ is directed subset iff μ so is

The following theorem is a generalization of the corresponding result in Proposition 1.9.

Theorem 2.14 Let (X, \leq) be a *PRS*, and let $x, y \in X$. Then:

- (1) $x \leq y$ iff $x \in \downarrow y$ iff $\downarrow x \subseteq \downarrow y$ iff $y \in \uparrow x$ iff $\uparrow x \subseteq \uparrow y$.
- (2) $x \in \downarrow x \Leftrightarrow x \in \uparrow x$;
- (3) $\downarrow x \cap \uparrow x = \{x\}$.

Proof. Since $x \leq y \Leftrightarrow x \in \downarrow y \Leftrightarrow \downarrow x \subseteq \downarrow y$; and since $x \leq y \Leftrightarrow y \in \uparrow x \Leftrightarrow \uparrow x \subseteq \uparrow y$. The results obtained.

The following theorem is a generalization of the corresponding result in Proposition 1.10 and Proposition 1.11.

Theorem 2.15. Let (X, \leq) be a *TR*, and let $\{(X_j, \leq_j) : j \in J\}$ be a family of *TR*, and let $\lambda_j \subseteq X_j$

$\forall j \in J$. Then:

- (1) If $\lambda_j \subseteq US(X_j)$ (resp. $LS(X_j)$) $\forall j \in J$, then $\prod_{j \in J} (\lambda_j)$ is a an upper (resp. lower) subsets of $(\prod_{j \in J} X_j, \leq)$.
- (2) $\uparrow (\prod_{j \in J} \lambda_j) = (\prod_{j \in J} \uparrow (\lambda_j))$
- (3) $\downarrow (\prod_{j \in J} \lambda_j) = (\prod_{j \in J} \downarrow (\lambda_j))$
- (3) If $\lambda_j \subseteq US(X_j)$ (resp. $LS(X_j)$) $\forall j \in J$, then $\prod_{j \in J} (\lambda_j)$ is a an upper (resp. lower) subsets of $(\prod_{j \in J} X_j, \leq)$.

Proof (1) Let $\lambda_j \subseteq US(X_j)$ (resp. $LS(X_j)$) $\forall j \in J$. Hence $\uparrow (\lambda_j) \subseteq (\lambda_j)$ (resp. $\downarrow (\lambda_j) \subseteq (\lambda_j)$),

then $\uparrow (\prod_{j \in J} \lambda_j) \subseteq (\prod_{j \in J} (\lambda_j))$ (resp. $\downarrow (\prod_{j \in J} \lambda_j) \subseteq (\prod_{j \in J} (\lambda_j))$). Thus $\prod_{j \in J} (\lambda_j)$ is an upper (resp. lower) subsets of $\prod_{j \in J} X_j$.

(2) and (3) Obvious;

The following theorem is a generalization of the corresponding result in Proposition 1.3. and Remark 1.1.

Theorem 2.16 Let (X, \leq) be a *TR*, and let $\lambda, \mu \subseteq X$. If $\lambda \subseteq \mu$ and μ is convex. Then

- (1) $\uparrow (\lambda) \subseteq \mu$;
- (2) $\bigvee(\phi) = le(X)$.

Proof (1) Let $x \in \uparrow (\lambda)$. Since $x \in (\downarrow \lambda)$, So $\exists y \in \lambda$ such that $x \leq y$. And since $x \in (\uparrow \lambda)$, So $\exists z \in \lambda$ such that $z \leq x$. since $\lambda \subseteq \mu$ implies that $z, y \in \mu$. And since μ is convex, then $x \in \mu$. Hence $\uparrow (\lambda) \subseteq \mu$.

(2) Obvious.

The following theorem is a generalization of the corresponding result in Proposition 1.12.

Theorem 2.17 Let (X, \leq) be a *TR*. and let $\lambda, \mu \subseteq X$. If μ is directed subset and cofinal in λ , then λ is directed subset and $\bigvee(\lambda) = \bigvee(\mu)$.

Proof Since $\mu \subseteq \lambda$, then $\lambda \neq \phi$. Let $x, y \in \lambda$ such that $x \neq y$. Then $\exists b_1, b_2 \in \mu$ such that x such that $x \leq b_1$, $y \leq b_2$ and $z \in \lambda \cap ub(\{b_1, b_2\})$. Hence μ is directed subset. Also, since $\mu \subseteq \lambda$, then $ub(\{\lambda\}) \subseteq ub(\{\mu\})$ (1) and let $y \notin ub(\{\lambda\})$ implies that $\exists a \in \lambda$ such that $a \not\leq y$ implies that $\exists a \in (\downarrow \mu)$ such that $a \not\leq y$ implies that $\exists b \in \mu$ such that $a \leq b$ and $a \not\leq y$ implies that $b \in \mu$ such that $b \not\leq y$ implies that $y \notin ub(\{\mu\})$ (2). From (1) and (2) implies that $ub(\{\lambda\}) = ub(\{\mu\})$. Hence $\bigvee(\lambda) = \bigvee(\mu)$.

Theorem 2.18 Let (X, \leq) be a *TR*. and let $\lambda, \mu \subseteq X$.

- (1) If $x \in ub(\lambda) \cap \lambda$ and If $x \leq x$. Then $x \in \bigvee(\lambda)$
- (2) If $ub(\lambda) = ub(\mu)$. Then $\bigvee(\lambda) = \bigvee(\mu)$.

Proof Obvious.

3- The way below relation and some types of functions on *TR*

Definition 3.1 Let (X, \leq) be a *TR*,

(1) Let $x, y \in X$. We say x way below (resp. y is way above) y (resp. x), denoted by $x \ll y$ iff $\forall D \subseteq X$, s.t. D is directed subset of X , if $y \leq \downarrow (\bigvee D)$, $\exists d \in D$ s.t. $x \leq d$.

The family of all elements in X each of which way above (resp. way below) x is denoted and defined as follows:
 $\uparrow x = \{y \in X : x \ll y\}$ (resp. $\downarrow x = \{y \in X : y \ll x\}$).

(2) Let $x \in X$. If $x \ll x$, then x is said to be isolated. The family of all isolated points above (resp. below) $x \in X$ is denoted $K(X)$ and defined by: $\uparrow^\circ x = \{y \in X : y \ll y \text{ and } x \leq y\}$ (resp. $\downarrow^\circ x = \{y \in X : y \ll y \text{ and } y \leq x\}$).

Theorem 3.1. Let (X, \leq) be a *TR*. let $x, y, z \in X$. Then :

- (1) If $x \leq y$ and $y \ll z$, then $x \ll z$;
- (2) If $x \ll y$ and $y \leq z$, then $x \ll z$;

- (3) If $\bigvee(\{y\}) \neq \phi$. and $x \ll y$, then $x \leq y$;
 (4) If $\bigvee(\{y\}) \neq \phi$. or $\bigvee(\{z\}) \neq \phi$, $x \ll y$ and $y \ll z$, then $x \ll z$.

Proof (1) Let D be a directed subset of X s.t. $z \in \downarrow \bigvee(D)$. Then $\exists d \in D$ s.t. $y \leq d$. Then $x \leq d$ and hence $x \ll z$.
 (2) Let D be a directed subset of X s.t. $z \in \downarrow \bigvee(D)$. Then $\exists k \in \bigvee(D)$ s.t. $z \leq k$. Thus $y \leq k$ and so $y \in \downarrow \bigvee(D)$. Therefore $\exists l \in D$ s.t. $x \leq l$. hence $x \ll z$.
 (3) Let $D = \{y\}$ and assume that $x \ll y$. Then $\exists d \in D$ s.t. $x \leq d$ but $y = d$. Thus $x \leq y$;
 (4) The proof follow directly From (1) and (3) above.

Definition 3.2 A TR (X, \leq) is called a domain iff for every directed subset λ of X , $\bigvee(\lambda) \neq \phi$.

Lemma 3.1 Let (X, \leq) be a TR , let $\downarrow x$ be a directed subset of $\forall x \in X$. Then $\forall z \in X$, $D = \bigcup \{\downarrow a : a \in \downarrow z\}$ is called directed subset.

Proof Let $\lambda, \mu \in D$ s.t., $\lambda \neq \mu$. Then $a_1, a_2 \in \downarrow z \in \text{ub}(\{\lambda, \mu\}) \cap \downarrow a \subseteq \text{ub}(\{\lambda, \mu\}) \cap D$. Thus D is called directed subset.

Lemma 2.2. Let (X, \leq) be a TR , let $\forall x \in X$. Then $\forall x \in X$, $\text{ub}(\bigcup \{\downarrow a : a \in \downarrow x\}) = \text{ub}(\bigcup \{\bigvee(\downarrow a) : a \in \downarrow x\})$. Thus $\bigvee(\bigcup \{\downarrow a : a \in \downarrow x\}) = \bigvee(\bigcup \{\bigvee(\downarrow a) : a \in \downarrow x\})$.

s.t., $\lambda \in \downarrow a_1$ and $\mu \in \downarrow a_2$. If $a_1 = a_2$, the result holds. the otherwise let $a \in \text{ub}(\{a_1, a_2\}) \cap \downarrow z$ so that Theorem 3.1 (2). $\lambda, \mu \in \downarrow a$. Since $\downarrow a$ is called directed subset, then $\exists \rho$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda \in \text{ub}(\bigcup \{\downarrow a : a \in \downarrow x\}) &\Leftrightarrow \forall \mu \in \bigcup \{\downarrow a : a \in \downarrow x\}, \\ \lambda \geq \mu &\Leftrightarrow \forall \mu \in (\downarrow a), a \in (\downarrow x), \\ \lambda \geq \mu &\Leftrightarrow \forall \rho \in \bigvee(\downarrow a), a \in (\downarrow x), \\ \lambda \geq \rho &\Leftrightarrow \lambda \in \text{ub}(\bigcup \bigvee(\downarrow a) : a \in \downarrow x). \end{aligned}$$

The following theorem is a generalization of the corresponding result in Proposition 1.13.

Theorem 3.2. Let (X, \leq) be a TR . let $le(X) \neq \phi$. Then $\forall \perp \in le(X)$, $\forall x \in X$, $\perp \ll x$.

Proof Let $x \in \downarrow \bigvee(D)$, where D is directed subset of X . $\exists d \in D$ s.t. $\perp \leq d$ for some $\perp \in le(X)$. Hence $\perp \ll x$.

The following theorem is a generalization of the corresponding result in Proposition 1.14.

Theorem 3.3. Let (X, \leq) be a TR . such that \leq is antisymmetric relation. If D is directed subset of X and $x \in \bigvee(D) \cap K(X)$, then $x \in D$.

Proof Let $x \in \downarrow \bigvee(D)$, where D is directed subset of X . $\exists d \in D$ such that. $x \leq d \leq x \leq \leq$ Hence $x \in D$.

Theorem 3.4. Let (X, \leq) be a TR , and let $\{(X_j, \leq_j) : j \in J\}$ be a family of TR , If $\forall j \in J$, X_j is a domain, then $\prod_{j \in J} (X_j)$ is a domain.

Proof Let λ be directed subset of $\prod_{j \in J} (X_j) = \{f : J \rightarrow \prod_{j \in J} (X_j) \text{ such that } f(j) \in X_j \forall j \in J\}$. Then one can deduce that $\forall j \in J$, $\lambda_j = \prod_{j \in J} (\lambda) = \{f(j) : f \in \lambda\}$ is a directed subset of X_j . So, $\bigvee(\lambda_j) \neq \phi$. Let $k_j \in \bigvee(\lambda_j) \forall j \in J$ so that $(k_j)_{j \in J} \in \bigvee(\lambda)$, that mean $\forall \lambda$ be directed subset, $\bigvee(\lambda_j) \neq \phi$. Hence $\prod_{j \in J} (X_j)$ is a domain.

Definition 3.3. Let (X, \leq_1) and (X, \leq_2) be TR , $x_1, x_2 \in X$ and let $f : (X, \leq_1) \rightarrow (Y, \leq_2)$ be a function. Then

- (1) f is t -monotone iff $f(x_1) \leq_2 f(x_2)$, whenever $x_1 \leq_1 x_2$, and $x_2 \leq_1 x_2$,
- (2) f is called order preserving (monotone) iff $f(x_1) \leq_2 f(x_2)$, whenever $x_1 \leq_1 x_2$.

Theorem 3.5. Let (X, \leq_1) and (X, \leq_2) be TR , and let $f : (X, \leq_1) \rightarrow (Y, \leq_2)$ be a function. If f is t -monotone, then $\downarrow(f(\lambda)) = \downarrow(f(\downarrow(\lambda))) \forall \lambda \subseteq X$ such that $\forall x \in \lambda, x \leq_1 x$

Proof Let $\lambda \subseteq X$ such that $\forall x \in \lambda, x \leq_1 x$. So, $\lambda \subseteq \downarrow(\lambda)$. Then $\downarrow(f(\lambda)) \subseteq \downarrow(f(\downarrow(\lambda)))$. We need to prove $\downarrow(f(\downarrow(\lambda))) \subseteq \downarrow(f(\lambda))$. So, let $y \in \downarrow(f(\downarrow(\lambda)))$ implies that $\exists n \in f(\downarrow(\lambda))$ such that $y \leq_2 n$ implies that $\exists l \in \downarrow(\lambda)$ such that $f(l) = n$ and $y \leq_2 n$ implies that $\exists k \in (\lambda)$ such that $l \leq_1 k, n = f(l) \leq_2 f(k)$ and $y \leq_2 n$ implies that $\exists h = f(k) \in f(\lambda)$ such that $y \leq_2 h$ implies that $y \in \downarrow(f(\lambda))$.

Theorem 3.6. Let (X, \leq_1) and (X, \leq_2) be PRS , then a function $f : (X, \leq_1) \rightarrow (Y, \leq_2)$ is t -monotone, iff it is monotone.

Proof Obvious

Theorem 3.7. Let (X, \leq_1) and (X, \leq_2) be PRS , and let $f : (X, \leq_1) \rightarrow (Y, \leq_2)$ be a function. Then f is monotone, iff $\downarrow(f(\lambda)) = \downarrow(f(\downarrow(\lambda))) \forall \lambda \subseteq X$.

Proof From Theorem 3.5 and Theorem 3.6 and the other direction, Let $x_1, x_2 \in X$ such that $x_1 \leq_1 x_2$. Now, $x_1 \in \downarrow x_2$ implies that $f(x_1) \in f(\downarrow(x_2)) \subseteq \downarrow(f(\downarrow(x_2))) = \downarrow(f(x_2))$ implies that $f(x_1) \leq_2 f(x_2)$.

Definition 3.4. Let (X, \leq_1) and (X, \leq_2) be TR , and let a function $f : (X, \leq_1) \rightarrow (Y, \leq_2)$ is called:

- (1) idempotent iff $f \circ f = f$;
- (2) below the identity iff $f \leq id_X$, that mean $\forall x \in X, f(x) \leq x$;
- (3) Projection iff f is idempotent and monotone;
- (4) Kernal operator iff f is idempotent, below the identity and monotone.

The following theorem is a generalization of the corresponding result in Lemma 1.1

Theorem 3.8. Let X be a set and let $f : X \rightarrow X$ be a function. Then f is idempotent iff $f(X) = fix(f)$, where $fix(f) = \{x \in X : f(x) = x\}$.

Proof \Rightarrow : First let $y \in f(X)$. Then $\exists x \in X$ such that $f(x) = y$. Now, $f(x) = y = f(f(x)) = f(y)$ so that $y = f(y)$ so that $y \in fix(f)$. Hence $f(X) \subseteq fix(f)$. Second, let $y \in fix(f)$. Then $y = f(y)$ so that $y \in f(X)$. Thus $fix(f) \subseteq f(X)$.

\Leftarrow : let $z \in X$. Then $f \circ f(z) = f(f(z)) = f(z)$. Hence f is idempotent

Definition 3.5. Let (X, \leq) be TR , and let $\lambda \subseteq X$. Then the relation \leq_λ on λ is defined by $\leq_\lambda = (\leq) \cap (\lambda \times \lambda)$.

Theorem 3.9. Let (X, \leq) be TR , and let $\lambda \subseteq X$. Then (λ, \leq_λ) is a TR .

Proof Let $(x, y), (y, z) \in (\leq) \cap (\lambda \times \lambda) = \leq_\lambda$. Then $(x, z) \in \leq$ so that $(x, z) \in \leq_\lambda$. Hence (λ, \leq_λ) is a TR .

Theorem 3.10. Let (X, \leq) be *PRS* (resp. poset), and let $\lambda \subseteq X$. Then (λ, \leq_λ) is *PRS* (resp. poset).

Proof (1) Assume that \leq is antisymmetric Let $(x, y), (y, x) \in (\leq_\lambda)$. Then $(x, y), (y, x) \in \leq$ so that $x = y$. Hence if \leq is antisymmetric, then \leq_λ so is.

(2) Assume that \leq is reflexive Let $x \in \lambda$. Then $(x, x) \in \lambda \times \lambda$. so that $\cap \leq = \leq_\lambda$. Hence if \leq is reflexive, then \leq_λ so is. From (1), (2) and Theorem 3.9, the result hold.

Remark 3.1. Let X be a set, $\lambda, \mu \subseteq X$, let (λ, \leq_λ) is sub-poset of a poset (X, \leq) such that $x \in \bigvee_\lambda(\mu)$ for some $\mu \subseteq \lambda$, but $x \notin \bigvee_X(\mu)$. So give the following example.

Example 3.1 Let $X = \{x, y, z, l\}, \lambda = \{x, y, z\}, \mu = \{x, y\}$ Now $\leq = \{(x, x), (y, y), (z, z), (l, l), (x, l), (y, l), (l, z), (x, z), (y, z)\}$. Then $\lambda \times \lambda = \{(x, x), (x, y), (x, z), (y, x), (y, y), (y, z), (z, x), (z, y), (z, z)\}$. Hence $\leq_\lambda = \{(x, x), (x, z), (y, y), (y, z), (z, z)\}$. Thus $\bigvee_\lambda(\mu) = z$ but $\bigvee_X(\mu) = l$.

References

- [1] S. Abramsky and A. Jung, domain theory in the Handbook for logic in Computer Science, Volume 3, Edited by S. Abramsky, Dov M. Gabbay, and T. S. E. Maibaum, published by Clarendon Press, Oxford in 1994.
- [2] B. Branachewski and R. E. Hofmann (eds), Continuous lattices, Lecture Notes in Mathematics 871, Springer-Verlag, Berlin, Heidelberg, New York, 1981.
- [3] M. Erne, Scott convergence and Scott Topologies in Partially ordered sets II, in [BH] [2], pp. 61-96.
- [4] G. Gierz, K. H. Hofmann, K. Keimel, J. D. Lawson, M. Mislove, and D. s. Scott, A compendium of continuous lattices, Springer Verlag, Berlin, Heidelberg, New York, 1980.
- [5] R. Heckmann, Power domain constuctions Ph. D. thesis, University Saarlandes, 1999.
- [6] <http://rwt.cs.unisb.de/heckman/diss/diss.html>.
- [7] R. E. Hofmann, Continuous Poset completely distributive complete lattices and Hausdorff compactifications, in [3], pp. 159-208.
- [8] R. E. Hofmann, Projective sober spaces, continuous lattices, Proc. Conf., Bremen 1979, Lect. Notes Math., 871 (1981), pp. 125-158.
- [9] R. E. Hofmann, Sobrification of partially ordered sets, Semi-group Forum, Volume 17 (1979) 123-138.
- [10] R. Kummetz, Partially ordered sets with projections and their topology, pd. D. thesis; Dresden University of Technology, 2000.
- [11] K. Larsen and G. Winskel, Using information systems to solve recursive domain equations effectively, in G. Kahn, D. B. Mac-Queen and G. Plotkin, eds, Semantics of data types, Lecture Notes in Computer Science 173, Springer -Verlag, Berlin, 1984, 109-129.
- [12] J. D. Lawson, The duality of continuous posets, Houston. J. Math., Volume5, No. 3(1979) 357-386.
- [13] J. D. Lawson, The Versatile continuous order, in Lecture Notes in Computer Science 298, Springer -Verlag, Berlin, heidelberg, New Yourk, 1987, pp 134-160.
- [14] S. Lipschutz, Theory and problems of general topology, Schaum series, McJRAW-HILL INT., 1965.
- [15] G. Markowsky [1981a], A motivation and generalization of Scott's notion of a continuous lattice, in [1979, Bremen], in [BH] [2], pp. 298-307.
- [16] J. Nino-Salcedo, On continuous posets and their applications, Ph.D. thesis, Tulane University, 1981.
- [17] S. Vickers. Information systems for continuous posets, Theoretical Computer Science 114, SIssue 2 (1993)201-299.

- [18] P. Waszhiewicz, Quantitative continuous domain, Ph.D. thesis School of Computer Science, University of Birmingham Edgbas-ton 2002.
- [19] Xiangyun Xie, Bijan Davvaz and Jian Tang, A study on (fuzzy) quasi- Γ -hyperideals in ordered Γ -semihypergroups, *Journal of Intelligent and Fuzzy Systems* 32(6):3821-3838 May 2017.
- [20] Yanfeng Luo, Jian Tang and Asghar Khan, Characterizations of semisimple ordered semihypergroups in terms of fuzzy hyperideals, *Journal of Intelligent and Fuzzy Systems*, *Journal of Intelligent and Fuzzy Systems* 30(3):1735-1753 March 2016.
- [21] Xiangyun Xie, Bijan Davvaz and Jian Tang, An investigation on hyper S-posets over ordered semihypergroups, *Open Mathematics* 15(1) February 2017
- [22] Shuhua Su, Qingguo Li, Algebraic fuzzy directed-complete posets, *Neural Computing and Applications*, Volume 21, Supplement 1, pp 255–265 August 2012.
- [23] L. Guo, G. Q. Zhang, and Q. G. Li, Fuzzy closure systems on L-ordered sets, *Mathematical Logic Quarterly*, vol. 57, no. 3, pp. 281–291, 2011.
- [24] G. Gierz, K. H. Hofmann, K. Keimel, J. D. Lawson, M. Mislove, and D. S. Scott, *Continuous Lattices and Domains*, vol. 93 of *Encyclopedia of Mathematics and its Applications*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK, 2003.
- [25] H. Lai and D. X. Zhang, Complete and directed complete Ω -categories, *Theoretical Computer Science*, vol. 388, no. 1–3, pp. 1–25, 2007.
- [26] P. Waszkiewicz, On domain theory over Girard quantales, *Fundamenta Informaticae*, vol. 92, no. 1-2, pp. 169–192, 2009.
- [27] D. Hofmann and P. Waszkiewicz, Approximation in quantale-enriched categories, *Topology and Its Applications*, vol. 158, no. 8, pp. 963–977, 2011.
- [28] D. Hofmann and P. Waszkiewicz, A duality of quantale-enriched categories, *Journal of Pure and Applied Algebra*, vol. 216, no. 8-9, pp. 1866–1878, 2012.
- [29] S. H. Su and Q. G. Li, Algebraic fuzzy directed-complete posets, *Neural Computing and Applications*, vol. 21, no. 1, supplement, pp. 255–265, 2012.
- [30] W. Yao, Quantitative domains via fuzzy sets—part I: continuity of fuzzy directed complete posets, *Fuzzy Sets and Systems*, vol. 161, no. 7, pp. 973–987, 2010.
- [31] K. R. Wager, Solving recursive domain equations with enriched categories [Ph.D. thesis], School of Computer Science, Carnegie-Mellon University, Pittsburgh, Pa, USA, 1994.
- [32] M. Erne, Z-continuous posets and their topological manifestation, *Applied Categorical Structures*, vol. 7, no. 1-2, pp. 31–70, 1999.
- [33] D. S. Scott, Outline of a mathematical theory of computation, in *Proceedings of the 4th Annual Princeton Conference on Information Sciences and Systems*, pp. 169–176, Princeton University Press, Princeton, NJ, USA, 1970.
- [34] D. S. Scott, Continuous lattices, in *Toposes, Algebraic Geometry and Logic*, vol. 274 of *Lecture Notes in Mathematics*, pp. 97–136, Springer, Berlin, Germany, 1972.
- [35] H. Zhang, Dualities of domains, Ph. D. thesis, Department of Mathematics, Tulane University, 1993.